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Returns and Return Policies

The EU-Georgia readmission agreement as a showcase of the strengths and weaknesses of the EU neighbourhood policy

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Authors

Marta Jaroszewicz, Mateusz Krępa, Marta Pachocka

Centre of Migration Research, University of Warsaw

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The EU-Georgia readmission agreement as a showcase of the strengths and weaknesses of the EU neighbourhood policy

Marta Jaroszewicz, Mateusz Krępa, Marta Pachocka

Centre of Migration Research, University of Warsaw

1. Introduction

Georgia is a small Eastern Partnership country situated outside the main migration routes to the EU, yet Georgians consistently remain among the most frequently returned nationalities from EU countries. Georgia has been implementing the 2011 readmission agreement with the EU without major reservations and as such can be called a showcase partner in EU return diplomacy and more widely a success story regarding the externalisation of EU migration policy. The European Commission has, in fact, constantly praised Georgia for the smooth and well-organised readmission of its citizens from EU territory (Gvelesiani 2020; EC 2013). Georgian authorities report that approximately 97% of readmission applications have been approved over the decade following the implementation of the agreement (SCMI 2021). The readmission agreement was accompanied by the visa facilitation agreement and builds on earlier cooperation within the Mobility Partnership and European Neighbourhood Policy Action Plan (Weinar 2011).

There are no publicly available sources that would validate the argument that Georgia had raised any major reservations or actively advocated for changes to the readmission agreement, which was a standard one that the EU had been proposing to both its South-Eastern and Eastern neighbours but also other countries under the so-called EU Readmission Agreements (EURAs) (Carrera 2016), with Ukraine and Moldova entering into similar negotiations earlier than Georgia (Gvelesiani 2020; Chelidze 2013). The readmission agreement's implementation has largely followed a technical, routine-based approach promoted by the EU in its relations with third countries (Carrera 2016; Trauener & Kruse 2008).

Cooperation with the EU under the readmission agreement, centred on the swift transfer of individuals, does not necessarily aid Georgia in tackling its broader migration-related challenge or the wider socio-political transformations confronting it. Nevertheless, it did align with Georgia's broader efforts to conclude an Association Agreement and potentially obtain EU candidate status. This raises an important question: to what extent has this routinised technical approach of the EU to promoting readmission agreements as part of its overall migration externalisation strategy weakened its ability to present a more comprehensive offer—one that addresses not only migration management but also the broader geopolitical concerns of Eastern European countries? This question is particularly relevant in the context of the current rapprochement between Georgia and Russia, as well as the rapid rise of authoritarian tendencies in the country (EC 2024).

The presented research digest provides insights into how and why Georgia accepted an EU-wide readmission agreement in 2011, and how this can be contextualised within the broader framework of the externalisation of EU migration policy and its neighbourhood policy on one hand, and the wider transformation of a post-Soviet country characterised by high levels of emigration and persistent security threats stemming from its geopolitical position on the other. The paper begins with a contextual background that reflects on the concept of the externalisation of the European Union's migration policy, with particular focus on the Eastern

neighbourhood. It then provides a concise overview of the migration context in Georgia. The subsequent section presents an analysis of the 2011 EU–Georgia Readmission Agreement. The discussion concludes with a set of final observations.

2. Contextual background. Externalisation of the EU’s migration policy and its Eastern neighbourhood

Since at least the early 2000s, the EU has been actively working to develop the foundations for the externalisation of its migration policy (with the readmission agreements being one of its main instruments), which has also been embedded in broader reflections on the stabilisation of its neighbourhood. However, these objectives have at times conflicted with one another.

As highlighted by Carrera (2016), strengthening cooperation with third countries of origin and transit regarding readmission has remained a constant key policy priority in the EU’s external relations and has been considered a crucial tool for improving return processes and ensuring the effectiveness of the EU’s expulsion policies. Whether the latter assumption remains true is not so straightforward, especially when taking into consideration human rights concerns and the well-being of returned persons, as well as the sustainability of return. In their recent assessment of the effectiveness of the “return rate”, Stutz and Trauner (2022) argue that the EU readmission arrangements may have less impact than widely assumed. Additionally, they follow strong regional patterns. Only in Eastern Europe and the Western Balkans has closer cooperation on readmission appeared to lead to consistently higher return rates.

It was only after the Amsterdam Treaty of 1999 that the European Community obtained the competence to sign EU-wide readmission agreements. The mandate that the European Commission received from the Member States to negotiate such agreements was rather rigid, essentially functioning as a draft model for readmission agreement. In 2000, the EC received its first mandate to begin negotiating readmission agreements with Morocco, Sri Lanka, Russia, and Pakistan, and later with Hong Kong and Macau (Trauner & Kruse 2008). The EU’s approach—under which it not only sought the return of its own citizens but also proposed the readmission of third-country nationals (TCNs) who transited through a given country—was met with reluctance and a lack of enthusiasm from third countries. In this context, from 2002 the EU began including an incentive in its proposals: the possibility of signing visa facilitation agreements (Trauner & Kruse 2008; Gvelesiani 2020). This addition proved to be something of a game changer. From that point on, a more or less consistent model of the EU Readmission Agreement (EURA) emerged. EURAs became incentive-based instruments, often linked to broader cooperation frameworks involving migration and border management, operational and financial support, visa facilitation or liberalisation, and mobility partnerships (Wolff 2014).

In practice, it turned out that the countries with which the EU aimed to sign visa agreements alongside readmission accords had different position vis-a-vis readmission, and the double-track approach was not always applied. A certain division emerged: Eastern Partnership and Western Balkan countries followed the route of visa facilitation agreements combined with readmission agreements, while Southern partners—and major players like Russia, China, and Pakistan—pursued different paths. In this context, a specific model of externalisation developed, particularly in Eastern Europe and the Caucasus, under the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP). This model was further refined with the creation in 2009 of the

Eastern Partnership initiative (encompassing Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus¹, Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine). It has been primarily tested on the Western Balkan countries (Trauner & Kruse 2008) and, to a certain extent, replicated in Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia (Trauner 2014). According to Hernández and Sagraera (2010), the EU's negotiations with Russia before the signing of the 2005 readmission agreement, for instance in the context of introducing obligations relating to readmission of TCNs or travel documents' security standards, also served as an agenda setting experience and have influenced the EU approach towards the entire region.

Unlike in the Mediterranean neighbourhood, migration deterrence and cooperation on irregular migration are not primary priorities for the EU in the Eastern Partnership (EaP) region. Instead, the focus is on the broader reform of migration management systems in neighbouring countries (Delcour 2013; Papagianni 2013). EU conditionality is achieved in this case through simultaneous visa liberalisation, with a warning that the visa-free regime could be revoked if necessary. If cooperation on readmission were found to be lacking, the EU would have the option to reintroduce visa requirements through a “visa suspension mechanism” (Stutz & Trauner 2021). However, this approach does not mean that the Eastern Partnership countries necessarily view readmission agreements as wholly beneficial. As Brunarska et al. (2013) highlight, in the eyes of countries that primarily serve as sending and/or transit states (which applies to all EaP countries), readmission was not a priority. It was largely perceived as serving the interests of the sending countries, while placing additional burdens on the receiving states—such as higher unemployment rates resulting from the return of their citizens. On the other hand, some EaP countries had, in the past, already concluded bilateral readmission agreements with EU Member States, in particular between neighbouring post-socialist states and post-Soviet countries. For instance, the Polish-Ukrainian bilateral readmission agreement had already been signed in 1993. In this sense, the change was largely statistical in nature—deported individuals began to be counted in EU-wide statistics rather than in bilateral ones (Jaroszewicz 2012). It should also be underlined that, in general, all Eastern Partnership countries have tended to comply with the provisions of the readmission agreements with the EU; in this respect, therefore, the case of Georgia is not exceptional. What makes it distinctive, however, is that in the case of other countries, such as Ukraine or Moldova, the number of readmission cases has been relatively small (European Commission 2011).

Finally, this digest also examines the EU–Georgia readmission agreement through the lens of migration diplomacy studies. While this emerging field is often associated with coercive strategies—where migration and refugee “crises” are instrumentalized to influence decision-making processes within the targeted host state (Greenhill 2010)—migration diplomacy can also take cooperative forms (Tsurapas 2017; Adamson & Tsurapas 2019). İçduygu and Aksel (2014), for example, illustrate how Turkey used negotiations with the EU over readmission agreements to advance its foreign policy goals. In the case of Georgia, EU migration diplomacy could be understood as a form of cooperative engagement, with the promise of granting Georgian citizens visa-free travel in exchange for accepting the stipulations of the readmission agreement. One could nonetheless argue that in the context of a small Eastern European state like Georgia—whose capacity to actively shape EU policies is limited due to power asymmetry

¹ After 2020 Belarusian presidential elections, the EU-Belarus relations were reviewed and revised by the EU. In 2021, the country's participation in the EaP was suspended by the Belarusian authorities. All this resulted in the factual suspension of readmission cooperation with Belarus.

—this cooperative diplomacy was somewhat constrained, as it ultimately required acquiescence to the EU’s vision of issue linkage and conditionality.

3. The migration situation in Georgia and the wider-readmission related context

Despite the recent dynamic inflow of Russian and Belarusian migrants—stimulated by Russia's full-scale aggression against Ukraine—Georgia remains primarily a country of emigration. Since regaining independence in 1991, high unemployment, political instability, ethnic conflicts, poverty, and low wages have led many Georgian citizens to seek better opportunities abroad (Khishtovani et al. 2022). Political unrest within the country, including ethno-political conflicts in two provinces—Abkhazia and South Ossetia—triggered a tragic crisis almost immediately after independence. Georgia was further affected by the Russian aggression against Georgia of 2008 and the global economic crisis, which together pushed the country into an economic recession. The armed conflict also resulted in the internal displacement of approx.132,000 people, adding to around 220,000 persons displaced earlier (UNHCR 2009), as well as Russia’s recognition of the independence of both South Ossetia and Abkhazia. According to the 2002 population census, as many as one million Georgians (out of a total population of 4.4 million) had left the country since 1989 (Salukvadze & Meladze 2014). Despite economic development in recent years, the outflow of people from Georgia increased by 7% from 2010 to 2020, with over 860,000 emigrants—amounting to over 20% of the country’s population (Khishtovani et al. 2022). As of 2017, the main destination countries for Georgian migrants were Russia (approximately 450,000), Greece (approx. 81,000), Ukraine (approx. 65,000), Germany (approx. 23,000), Cyprus (approx. 16,000), and Italy (approx. 12,000) (SCMI, 2019). The intensity of emigration increased even more after the introduction of visa-free travel to Schengen countries (Abesadze et al. 2023) and did not abate till recently, also due to current political turmoil. According to the data of the National Statistics Office of Georgia, immigration from Georgia doubled in 2023-2024, reaching as many as 245,064 persons leaving the country in 2023 (Civil.ge 2024). What changed, however, was the geographical distribution of migrants. From 2010 to 2020, the share of the post-Soviet area as a destination for Georgian emigration declined slightly from 75% to 72%, while the share of EU countries and the UK increased from 20% to 21% (Khishtovani et al. 2022). Finally, despite being a traditionally conservative society, Georgia underwent dramatic changes in the gender composition of migration, with both men and women increasingly undertaking labour migration. Remittances from migrants working abroad play a prominent role in Georgia’s economy. According to Radio Free Liberty (2023), in 2020 remittances constituted as much as 13% of Georgia’s GDP.

Although Georgia is not situated along the EU’s most critical migratory routes, the emigration of its citizens to EU countries has sparked certain concerns. Following the 2017 visa liberalisation agreement between the EU and Georgia, there was a noticeable rise in worries about the involvement of Georgian organised crime groups within EU member states (IOM 2019). Additionally, the number of asylum applications submitted by Georgian nationals increased after visa-free travel to the EU/Schengen area was introduced. Georgians also rank among the most frequently returned nationals from the EU, which may reflect both the effective enforcement of the EU-Georgia readmission agreement and Georgia's well-functioning return system in terms of return rates and procedural efficiency, despite some critical voices about the sustainability of the re-integration component (Krepa et al. 2024).

Although Georgian citizens have generally not ranked among the top three nationalities receiving return orders in the EU, they have consistently placed first or second in terms of actual returns carried out. A similar pattern emerges with return decisions: while Georgians are not issued the highest number of orders, they remain—after Albanians—one of the most frequently returned groups (Eurostat 2023). Eurostat (2025) data for the first quarter of 2025 show that 2,170 Georgians were returned, making them the third most frequently returned non-EU nationality, followed by Syrians (2,000), Albanians (1,865), Turks (1,845), and Moroccans (1,110).

Comparative longitudinal data on persons transferred under readmission agreements is not available. Eurostat publishes data on those ordered to leave and those returned to a third country after such orders. However, it appears that the overall number of persons readmitted from EU Member States to Georgia has stabilised at a similar level. According to data provided to the GAPs research team at the CMR UW by the Ministry of Interior of Georgia in 2023, Georgia received 4,183 readmission requests from EU Member States, including 2,771 from Germany, 635 from France, 175 from Greece, and 106 from Poland (data quoted after Krępa et al. 2024). The growth in the number of readmitted persons also indicates that over the years the transfer system has matured and is now implemented based on an electronic case management system. Initial readmission requests were smaller in scale — for instance, 1271 deportations from the EU to Georgia were recorded in 2010 under bilateral agreements, and 768 in 2011 (Brunarska et al. 2013).

Although Georgia receives technical support from the EU and specific MS, it struggles with reintegrating returned migrants in the context of insufficiently funded and often ineffective programmes that fall short of meeting returnees' needs, coupled with poor access to information about available support both pre-departure and upon arrival. Additionally, challenges arise from the mismatch between migrants' qualifications and local labour market demands, and the societal pressure on returnees who are often mistakenly perceived as wealthy, which can lead to re-emigration (Krępa et al. 2024).

4. EU-Georgia readmission agreement

The EU–Georgia Readmission Agreement was signed on November 22, 2010, and entered into force on March 1, 2011 (Agreement 2011b). As early as 2006, the European Neighbourhood Policy Action Plan for Georgia stated that its purpose was to “strengthen the dialogue and cooperation in preventing and fighting against illegal migration, which could possibly lead in the future to an EC-Georgia agreement on readmission”. Negotiations began in November 2008 (Carrera 2016), with Georgia expressing readiness to conclude a readmission agreement following the launch of negotiations on the Mobility Partnership (Weinar 2011). The Mobility Partnership reaffirmed the commitment of both parties to conclude an agreement on the readmission of persons residing without authorisation, as well as to facilitate the issuance of visas (Joint Declaration on a Mobility Partnership between the European Union and Georgia 2009). The logic behind the Mobility Partnership lies in concluding bilateral agreements on circular migration, while also offering Georgia assistance with the reintegration of returning migrants. This was aimed at reducing pressure on Georgia’s financial and administrative resources when it comes to supporting its own citizens in legal migration processes and their reintegration upon return from abroad (Weinar 2011; Chelidze 2013). As for the Visa

Facilitation Agreement (Agreement 2011a), it provided for reduced visa fees for short-stay visas (€35 instead of €60), as well as simplified procedures for issuing multiple-entry visas to certain categories of persons.

Although the readmission agreement emphasised reciprocity (Agreement 2011b), its primary aim was clearly the effective return of Georgian citizens from the EU, rather than vice versa. The agreement outlines the means of establishing a migrant's nationality (Art. 8), time limits for the readmission procedure (Art. 10), modalities of transfer and modes of transportation (Art. 11), as well as transit procedures (Art. 14). It also established a Joint Readmission Committee responsible for monitoring the implementation of the agreement, deciding on implementing arrangements necessary for its uniform application, proposing amendments, and facilitating the exchange of information (Art. 18). The agreement included provisions concerning both Georgian nationals and third-country nationals. However, this aspect does not constitute a major challenge for Georgia—unlike in the cases of Ukraine or Russia, which requested transitional periods for accepting TCNs—since Georgia neither shares a land border with the European Union nor lies along key migration routes to the EU.

In general, the readmission agreement can be considered relatively ambitious in terms of the obligations it imposed on Georgia. These include requirements for the swift processing of readmissions, the acceptance of provided documentation, and the establishment of electronic case management systems. Notably, Article 2 of the agreement stipulates that Georgia must readmit its nationals upon application by the requesting EU Member State, with “no further formalities other than those provided for in this Agreement,” provided that nationality is either proven or reasonably assumed on the basis of *prima facie* evidence. Additionally, the agreement extends the scope of readmission to include minor unmarried children and spouses of Georgian nationals, even when the spouse holds a different nationality (Article 2.2). The agreement with Georgia was also notable for its modern provisions, like the use of computerised identity cards, biometric data, and tools such as the Visa Information System, which made the readmission process smoother and quicker than in other cases. The ambitious nature of the EU–Georgia agreement is further underscored by a 2014 study from the European Migration Network (EMN 2014), which compared the effectiveness of various EURAs. The study noted significant delays and administrative challenges in implementing the EURA with other countries—including average response times of over a year—whereas Georgia demonstrated a markedly more efficient system, with an average response time of just 6 to 7 days. As of 2021, Georgia has concluded the implementation of protocols with 12 EU Member States. Moreover, since 2013 the technical implementation of the agreement is supported by the Readmission Case Management Electronic System that eases the operations/actions in readmission and transit procedures (SCNI 2021).

Georgia's negotiating position during the readmission agreement talks with the European Commission is not extensively documented in publicly available sources. However, it is evident that Georgia's primary objective was alignment with the EU, as part of its broader efforts to conclude an Association Agreement and potentially obtain candidate status. In July 2010, while negotiations on the Readmission Agreement were still underway, the EU and Georgia also launched formal negotiations on an Association Agreement, including a Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) (European Commission 2011). This represented a major milestone for Georgia, which was aiming to revitalise its economy amid ongoing geopolitical tensions, particularly in the aftermath of the 2008 Russian aggression, and

persistently high unemployment levels. The significance of the readmission agreement is further emphasised by its inclusion in the EU–Georgia Association Agreement, which refers to its full implementation in Article 16 (Agreement 2014). Regarding visa facilitation, Delcour (2013) notes that the reduction in the cost of Schengen visas and the more flexible approach to issuing multiple-entry visas were not particularly important for Georgia, due to its distant geographical location and the overall high costs of travel. What was more significant, however, was the EU’s recognition of Georgia’s territorial integrity. Moreover, the country’s foreign policy priorities prior to 2008—particularly integration into NATO—became less viable following the conflict with Russia. In this context, the EU emerged, at least formally, as the most plausible alternative. As Tauner (2010) highlights, in light of the Russian aggression and the issuance of Russian passports to residents of Abkhazia and South Ossetia, the question of the attractiveness of Georgian citizenship became increasingly important.

In 2017 Georgia obtained a visa free regime with Schengen countries, according to which Georgian nationals with biometric passports can travel visa-free to the 26 countries of the Schengen Area and stay for 90 days in any 180-day period (EEAS 2017). Georgia applied for EU membership in March 2022 and was granted candidate status in December 2023. However, the accession process has since stalled due to concerns over democratic backsliding and limited progress in implementing EU reforms (EC 2024). Since 2012, the country has been ruled by the Georgian Dream party, which has increasingly favoured a cautious rapprochement with Russia—particularly following the contested 2024 presidential elections (Karadağ 2024). This shift has undermined Georgia’s EU integration prospects and slowed reform efforts. While the EU’s normative influence has yielded some positive outcomes, it has fallen short of meeting the geopolitical expectations of Eastern Partnership states, especially Georgia (Karadağ 2024). Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022 heightened Georgia’s geopolitical concerns, also prompting a more pragmatic view of migration cooperation with the EU (Lebanidze & Kakachia 2023). Georgia has positioned itself as a key partner in EU external migration management, notably through readmission agreements. Nonetheless, the post-2022 context highlights the need for stronger EU support in reintegrating returnees and addressing the social pressures caused by emigration.

5. Conclusion

The EU-Georgia readmission agreement, which came into force in 2011, is widely considered a success story within EU migration policy. The European Commission has consistently praised Georgia for its smooth and well-organised readmission of its citizens from EU territory. This is very important for the EU, since Georgian citizens consistently rank among the most frequently returned nationalities from EU countries. Georgia has exhibited a remarkably efficient implementation system, now operating through an electronic case management system, and the agreement places ambitious obligations on Georgia, including swift processing and acceptance of provided documentation. This readmission agreement was strategically paired with a visa facilitation agreement, building on earlier cooperation within a Mobility Partnership, which aimed to facilitate legal migration processes and assist Georgia with the reintegration of returning migrants.

Georgia's primary motivation for accepting this agreement was alignment with the European Union as part of its broader efforts to conclude an Association Agreement and potentially obtain candidate status, a goal made particularly crucial after the 2008 Russian aggression and in the face of persistent high unemployment and the need to seek out new opportunities for

economic development and alleviate social problems. The readmission agreement was also an important step towards establishing sustainable legal migration pathways for Georgian citizens. This process was significantly facilitated by the granting of a visa-free regime to Georgia in 2017. However, labour migration opportunities remain limited, as only a few EU member states have signed bilateral labour migration agreements with Georgia, such as Germany in 2023 (Federal Ministry of Interior 2023).

Nevertheless, the EU's "technical, routine-based approach" to cooperation under this agreement, focused primarily on rapid transfers, does not necessarily help Georgia address its broader migration-related challenges or the wider socio-political transformations it faces. For Georgia, as a country predominantly sending migrants, readmission was not considered a priority but rather an additional burden, potentially leading to increased unemployment among returnees. Furthermore, the introduction of visa-free travel to the EU/Schengen area was followed by a significant rise in asylum requests from Georgian citizens and notable concerns regarding the involvement of Georgian organised crime groups within EU member states.

Summing up, EU migration diplomacy with Georgia combined cooperation through travel incentives with constraint, as Georgia—lacking influence over EU policy—had to accept the EU's conditions on readmission, which did not address the broader social concerns of its society. The current geopolitical context, marked by concerns over democratic backsliding in Georgia and the ruling party's increasing rapprochement with Russia, further underscores the limitations of the EU's approach, as its normative influence has proven insufficient to meet Georgia's expectations and fully integrate the country. This highlights the ongoing need for stronger EU support in reintegrating returnees and alleviating the social pressures caused by emigration in Georgia. On a strategic level, treating the readmission–visa facilitation/visa free regime linkage on a purely technical basis may raise concerns, as Georgia is still effectively in the process of implementing its 2011 readmission agreement with the EU. In this sense, it remains a success story of EU migration policy, though not necessarily aligned with the broader EU agenda.

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